

Barcelona Supercomputing Center

Annual Report 2022
Bioinfo4Women Programme

Table of contents

01 INTRODUCTION	2
02 OBJECTIVES 2022	4
General Objectives	4
Communication Objectives	8
Internationalisation Objectives	12
Mentoring and Training Objectives	15
Research Line Objectives	16
03 OTHER ACHIEVEMENTS	18
04 PEER- REVIEWED PUBLICATIONS	20

01 INTRODUCTION

The Bioinfo4Women (B4W) programme has been a dedicated effort since 2018 to promote gender equality in the Life Science Department of the Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC), with special emphasis on raising awareness of research conducted by women within and outside the BSC. It started by organising seminars delivered by women researchers and financially supporting three B4W fellows (women who started their careers as independent researchers outside the BSC). Since then, it has grown in terms of scope and impact, and has diversified its activities thanks to the contributions from people of all career stages at the Life Science Department of the BSC.

The main mission of B4W is to highlight the work from women researchers by providing role models, training, and support to women researchers in all career stages to develop their scientific career, with a special focus on their transition from postdoctoral to junior independent positions. It works on the different fields of biology, with emphasis on the areas of personalised medicine, bioinformatics, and high-performance computing (HPC). The Programme receives the institutional support of the Life Science Department of the BSC and contributes to the fulfilment of the centre's objective of promoting the development of a scientific career in accordance with the [gender equality](#) plan developed.

The strategy and organization of the programme were shaped at the beginning of 2021. B4W organised a co-creation session with renowned researchers, including Prof. Janet Thornton (EMBL-EBI), Dr Janet Kelso (MPI EVA) and Dr Isabelle Vernós (CRG). During this session, participants identified the main problems and obstacles encountered by women researchers throughout their professional careers, as well as the elements or actions that allowed participants to overcome them and achieve professional success.

The strategy of the B4W programme was redefined after the analysis of the information collected in this co-creation session. It was organised around five strategic lines of action, and both ongoing and planned activities were redistributed around them.

The main actions undertaken within the year 2022, in terms of gender equality at the scientific level, can be grouped into four main categories: 1) organising **research seminars** delivered by women researchers, open to everyone, most of them [recorded](#) and widely disseminated, including an agenda to connect with other researchers at the BSC after the presentation; 2) establishing **contacts** with other international research institutes, both in terms of conducting joint research and establishing synergies with their institutional initiatives to promote women in science; 3) training young researchers in terms of career paths through an international pilot **mentoring** programme; and 4) conducting **research** on the sex and gender biases in AI, including training delivered to junior researchers from all BSC departments to raise awareness on the potential impact in of such biases in the data they use in their daily work.

This report summarises the main activities and achievements of the B4W programme throughout 2022.

02 OBJECTIVES 2022

At the beginning of 2022 the B4W executive committee defined specific objectives for the annual plan, most of which were achieved by the end of the year along with additional actions due to opportunities, as summarised below.

General Objectives

Objective 1. Make the Programme sustainable.

The executive committee of the B4W programme and its working groups have evolved during 2022, demonstrating the interest raised and consolidating it as a priority for the Life Science department.

Executive Committee: current members are Eva Alloza, Davide Cirillo, Atia Cortés, Maria Flores, Alba Jené and María José Rementeria. The modifications that took place in 2022 are:

- Nataly Buslón moved from the Executive Committee to the Human Resources department, as the BSC's gender officer.
- Eva Navarrete left the BSC.
- Davide Cirillo joined the Executive Committee.
- Atia Cortés joined the Executive Committee.

Communication Working Group:

- Leader: Eva Alloza.
- Members: Mónica Cabrera, Maria Sopena, Othmane Hayoun, Uciel Pablo Chorostecki, Lidia Lopez, Ana Dueso, Laura Portell, Atia Cortés, María Chavero.

Research Working Group:

- Leader: Davide Cirillo.
- Co-leader: Atia Cortés.
- Members: María José Rementeria, Maria Sopena, Fatemeh Baghdadi, Othmane Hayoun, Lidia Lopez, Ana Dueso, Ignasi Puch, Maria Morales, Roc Farriol, Victoria Ruiz, Eva Alloza, Marta Gonzalez, Olivier Philippe, Blanca Calvo, Beatriz Urda.

Internationalization Working Group:

- Leader: María José Rementeria.
- Co-leader: Gonzalo Parra.
- Members: Alba Jené, Fatemeh Baghdadi, Laura Portell, Olfat Khannous, Saioa Manzano.

Training and Mentoring Working Group:

- Leader: Alba Jené
- Co-leader: María José Rementeria
- Members: Eva Alloza, Átia Cortés, Anaïs Baudot, Vera Pancaldi, Olfat Khannous

Objective 2. Participation at the European Conference on Computational Biology (ECCB2022, 12-21st September 2022).

To inspire and encourage other organisations to adopt similar programmes in their contexts, the B4W programme actively contributed to ECCB2022 with the following activities:

- **“Birds of a Feather”** session: "Sex and Gender Biases in Technology and Artificial Intelligence". Facilitated by Gonzalo Parra, where Davide Cirillo presented the book published with the same title, María José Rementeria presented Diversity in research teams, and Mónica Cabrera presented the highlights of the European Student Council Symposium 2022 (SCS2022). The activity had 108 participants and was very successful and well received by the audience.

- **B4W posters:**
 - I. The Bioinfo4Women Programme.
<https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1119338.1>
 - II. The Bioinfo4Women research line on sex and gender bias in healthcare and AI.
<https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1119335.1>
 - III. The Bioinfo4Women pilot mentoring programme for young scientists.
<https://doi.org/10.7490/f1000research.1119332.1>

The collage consists of four posters:

- Poster 1 (Left):** Titled "Gender imbalance at different scales". It discusses the mission and vision of Bioinfo4Women, internationalization and networking, support for women's scientific careers, and strategy, organization, and financial engagement.
- Poster 2 (Middle-Left):** Titled "Research Working Group". It introduces the group, lists opportunities and challenges, and details actions for raising awareness and building best practices.
- Poster 3 (Middle-Right):** Titled "The Bioinfo4Women International Pilot Mentoring Programme for Young Scientists". It outlines the mission and vision, lists pilot objectives, and provides a timeline for the programme.
- Poster 4 (Right):** A summary poster titled "RESULTS" showing the evolution of the training program for mentorship members, including meeting expectations, workshop content, and training applicable to their future.

- **Online workshop:** A virtual workshop on “Sex and Gender Dimension in Biomedical Research” within the New Trends in Bioinformatics by ECCB, which was the programme of tutorials and workshops. The 3-hour event included a keynote talk by Sabine Oertelt-Prigione (Radboud University Medical Center, NL) followed by three B4W presentations dealing with “Socio-economic and ethical aspects” by Nataly Buslón, “Sex and gender bias in artificial intelligence” by Davide Cirillo and “The B4W Research working group” by Átia Cortés. The workshop closed with a hands-on session on bias detection by Fatemeh Baghdadi. Agenda: <https://eccb2022.org/ntb-w07>. Vídeo: <https://youtu.be/tGkwa1n3WYk?t=5>
- **Invited flash talk in the “Institutional talks” session:** The ECCB2022 organising committee invited B4W to showcase their activities within the main programme of the conference. Alba Jené delivered the talk “The Bioinfo4Women Programme: towards gender, equity and diversity in science” which caught the audience’s attention and brought the EDI topic to the scientific schedule of the conference. <https://youtu.be/PORGYiZJwUc?t=2690>.

- **B4W booth at the conference (along with the organisers):** The B4W had presence in the organisers' booth being present in the breaks with exhibitors, both interacting with delegates over the B4W overview poster, and two *meet the author* sessions inviting to informal discussions with Davide Cirillo about the recently published book "Sex and Gender Biases in Technology and Artificial Intelligence".

- **Naming the ECCB2022 conference meeting rooms:** Naming the conference rooms with names of outstanding women in the field of bioinformatics and science. The rooms names were:
 - Auditorium Anna Tramontano
 - Room Margaret O. Dayhoff
 - Room Rosalind Franklin
 - Poster area Rita Levi-Montalcini

The names were presented in the venue, digital final scientific programme and programme at a glance, on-line platform and conference application. Large panels were placed at the entrance of these conference spaces. Each large panel gave information about the women researchers that gave name to the rooms describing some of their most remarkable contributions to science.

Objective 3. Make successful trajectories visible to foster scientific vocations.

The **ECCB2022** conference highlighted the bioinformatics career path of distinguished women investigators to encourage young female researchers to pursue scientific careers. To achieve this, the conference meeting rooms were renamed with those of relevant researchers, such as Anna Tramontano, Margaret O. Dayhoff, Rosalind Franklin and Rita Levi-Montalcini. Large panels containing the researcher's name, an illustrated picture, a brief biography highlighting her most remarkable contributions, and a link to a relevant website, were created.

The B4W has safely stored the large panels for potential usage in the future.

The original idea to accomplish this objective was to publish short interviews/profiles of women scientists on the website, which is pending the visual upgrade, planned in Q1-2023.

Communication Objectives

Objective 1. Upgrade the Bioinfo4Women web page.

Unfortunately, this goal started but has not finished due to a lack of resources and time. The B4W's programme website is currently outdated, and this is an objective for Q1-2023 to be accomplished by a task force which was already been set up in Q42022.

Objective 2. Communicate success stories from B4W fellows.

The following interviews and public events took place in 2022 to disseminate and distribute B4W's information to the general public.

- **Capital Radio** interview. María José Rementería. March 2022
https://www.capitalradio.es/audio/20220406_DEEPBUSINESS/103281267
- **Digital Society Foundation** interview. Atia Cortés. April 2022
<https://digitalfuturesociety.com/es/videos/dfs-voices-necesitamos-un-enfoque-feminista-e-interseccional-para-mitigar-las-desigualdades-con-atia-cortes/>
- **La Directa News** interview. María José Rementería. September 2022.

- **Forbes List.** Atia Cortés <https://forbes.es/listas/170243/lista-forbes-los-40-mejores-futuristas-de-espana/>
- **Oficina 42 UOC Podcast.** María José Rementeria and Atia Cortés. November 2022. <https://blogs.uoc.edu/informatica/despacho-42-ia-medicina-personalizada/>
- **Radio Nacional de España.** Atia Cortés. Monthly programme. <https://www.rtve.es/play/audios/a-hombros-de-gigantes/hombros-gigantes-microbiota-nubes-19-11-22/6738369/>

Objective 3. Continue organising the yearly event around 11th February (Bioinfo Women’s Day).

B4W organised the department's open doors day, which has been going on from 2019. This was also a remote edition due to the restrictions imposed by the pandemic. At this event, women researchers presented their work to master and under-graduate students. During these presentations, students were organised into small groups, promoting informal discussions where the researcher explained her work and establishing an open dialogue with students. This activity is organised in the context of the International Day of Women and Girls in Science.

There were more than 50 registered participants of 17 nationalities, BSC female researchers presenting their work, and 18 (15 women and 3 men) virtual participants.

The event was also featured within the Spanish Ministry’s activities for the day (p91): <https://www.ciencia.gob.es/InfoGeneralPortal/documento/d4098c35-2d02-4111-9c50-563e8d2cad51>.

Objective 4. Organise a joint event with other departments at the BSC to visualise the research done by women at the research centre.

To commemorate the International Day of Action for Women's Health on May 28th, the B4W programme, in collaboration with the BSC departments, organised in 2022 for the first time the

Women's Health Awareness Week (WHAW), full of activities to raise awareness on the research around women's health and gender in the centre. The agenda can be found here: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7612637>.

The objectives of the activities were:

- To raise awareness on women's specific health problems in terms of the diagnosis, evolution and treatment of diseases.
- To share the knowledge developed by BSC researchers on the subject with all employees, visitors and collaborating institutions.
- To create connections with institutions that are engaged in the issue.

The activities were:

1. BSC research posters Women's Health

A series of posters were presented to showcase eight BSC research projects related to women's health. The poster's gallery was displayed in the digital totem placed in the BSC-Repsol building's reception during the whole week.

2. WHAW Quiz - How much do you know about health in women and men?

The WHAW Quiz consisted of a ten-question questionnaire about women's and men's health and sex differences. The quiz was open to all BSC and received over 40 participations. The quiz winner received the book "Unwell Women: A Journey Through Medicine" in the award ceremony during the closing session. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7529568>

3. Series of seminars about Health and Women:

- Hybrid webinar at the BSC introduced by Alfonso Valencia including two talks:
 - o Biases in health and Artificial Intelligence. Speaker: Davide Cirillo, BSC.
 - o Differences in mental illness between men and women. Speaker: Simona Mellino, WBP.
 - o Link: <https://youtu.be/dmLtMBwHGOc>

WHAW.
Women's Health Awareness Week

WHAW Quiz
How much do you know about sex differences in health and disease?

Wednesday 25 May (Auditorium Repsol Building Floor -1)

- 16:00 h - 17:30 h **BSC Cineforum**
"Dona, vostè no té res!". A documentary film about sex and gender bias in medicine.

Thursday 26 May WHAW seminar - International Day of Action for Women's Health
Training room T-3-2. | Online | Chair: Antonio Valencia

- 12:00 h - 12:30 h **Seminar** "Sex and gender bias in artificial intelligence for health."
Speaker: Davide Cirillo, Head of the Machine Learning for Biomedicine Unit, Life Sciences Dept., BSC.
- 12:30 h - 13:00 h **Seminar** "Sex and gender differences in brain and mental health: Selected use cases on how to tackle them"
Speaker: Simona Mellino, Women's Brain Project Vice President.

Friday 27 May Terraza del BSC

- 10:00 h End of WHAW Quiz
- 13:00 h - 13:30 h Poster session
- 13:30 h - 14:00 h Closing event and award for WHAW Quiz winner.

#May28
#WomensHealthMatters

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- Webinar in collaboration with Sistema Navarro I+D+i en Salud.
 - o Jornada de Investigación en Salud con Dimensión de Género. Speakers: María José Rementería, Davide Cirillo.
 - o Link: <https://www.aditech.com/iniciativas/investigacion-con-dimension-de-genero/>.

- Webinar in collaboration with Pasteur Institute of Uruguay (Montevideo)
 - o La perspectiva de sexo y género en la ciencia e investigación biomédica para mejorar la precisión". Speakers: Nataly Buslón, Davide Cirillo. ***Link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6DEmiiKDC8M>.

4. CineForum

The CineForum on Women's Health aimed to open an internal dialogue among BSC employees about the subject. The activity planned to watch the documentary "Dona, vostè no té res" (<https://www.ccma.cat/tv3/alcanta/sense-ficcio/dona-voste-no-te-res/video/6146129/>) and follow-up with a round table. This activity was cancelled due to lack of registrations.

5. Closing session

The WHAW closed the activities with a cocktail where the researchers explained the posters of their research and the prize was awarded to the winner of the WHAW Quiz. The session was very successful, receiving praise also from the BSC Directors and one BSC SAB member, who also participated. There were more than 40 participants in total.

Internationalisation Objectives

Objective 1. Expand international collaboration.

B4W has established **collaborations** with the following institutions:

- **BBMRI-ERIC**. EOSC-Life Training course project “Integration of the sex and gender dimension on Life Sciences research”.
- **ELIXIR-DE (de.NBI)**. [WiDS conference](#) programme and pilot ELEAD mentoring programme within ELIXIR.
- **ADitech**. Invited to “Jornadas de Salud con Dimensión de Género”, aiming to repeat yearly.
- **ACM Women Barcelona**. B4W is part of this initiative, a specific chapter of ACM created in October 2022 that aims to promote women in HPC.
- **Observatorio Mujeres, Ciencia e Innovación (OMCI)**. Participation in the working Group UMyC: “Elaboración de una guía con recomendaciones prácticas para la integración de la dimensión de género en los proyectos de I+D+I”.

B4W has established **connections** with national and international organisations to explore future collaborations and the development of joint activities, with the following initiatives (amongst others): ACM Women Barcelona, Microsoft AI& Health, ELIXIR-DE (de.NBI), Women in Global Health (WGH), Women in HPC, Observatorio Mujeres, Ciencia e Innovación (OMCI), Women Brain Project (WBP).

B4W actively participated in several **conferences**, training courses, and other events that were organized by other institutions presenting the programme and/or the advances in the research line to increase the international collaboration of the programme:

- Congreso internacional de Ciencia, Feminismo y Masculinidades - **CICFEM 2022** (March 2022). “*Medicina Personalizada y Transgénero*” **selected talk** by researcher Dr Oriol Ríos.
- Round Table “Amb Mirada de Dona” – **Partit dels Socialistes de Catalunya PSC** (March, 2022). *María José Rementeria* as **panellist**. Link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RiY6_RoOLJY.
- Gender Summit - **Institut Pasteur Paris** (March 2022). “*Sex and Gender Perspective in Health & AI*” by Davide Cirillo and Nataly Buslón as **invited speaker**.

- Round Table “L’ecosistema català de ciència i enginyeria de dades”- **WiDS BCN** (April 2022). *Atia Cortés as **panellist***. <https://websk.upc.edu/wids-barcelona2022/>
- RltrainPlus Training course - **European School for Management of Research Infrastructures** (May 2022). “*Diversity/Gender Aspects, learnings from the Bioinfo4Women Initiative*” by *María José Rementeria as **invited speaker***. <https://ritrainplus.eu/2022/07/08/driving-excellence-for-research-infrastructures-and-core-facilities-ritrain-plus-workshop-report/>
- IV Academic Meeting at the Vichy – **Royal European Academy of Doctors** (May 2022). “*Sex and Gender bias in Health an Artificial Intelligence*” by *María José Rementeria as **invited speaker***. https://raed.academy/wp-content/uploads/2022/05/programa-Vichy-Catalan-2022-v3_cmpr.pdf.
- Women in Data Science (Perspectives in Industry and Academia part III) – **German Network for Bioinformatics Infrastructure de.NBI** (May 2022) by *Alba Jené and Marta Melé as **invited speaker***. <https://www.denbi.de/de-nbi-events-archive/1396-women-in-data-science-2022-perspectives-in-industrie-and-academia>.
- Jornada en Salud con Dimensión de Género - **ADItch** (May, 2022). “*Sex and gender dimension in health*” by *Davide Cirillo and María José Rementeria as **invited speaker***. <https://www.aditech.com/aditech-y-el-barcelona-supercomputing-center-colaboran-en-favor-de-la-excelencia-cientifica/>.
- Seminar - **Instituto Pateur Uruguay** (May, 2022). “*La perspectiva de sexo y género en la ciencia e investigación biomédica para mejorar la medicina de precisión*” by *Davide Cirillo and Nataly Buslón as **invited speaker***. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6DEmiiKDC8M>.
- Swiss bioinformatics summit workshop: “*In all fairness: sex and gender biases in data science and AI, and how to address them*” – **SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics** (June, 2022) by *Davide Cirillo as **invited speaker***. <https://sibdays.sib.swiss/workshops-tutorials>.
- **ISEA 2022**: “*Bioinfo4Women. Outstanding Young Female Bioinformaticians*” (June, 2022) by *Atia Cortés and María José Rementeria as **invited speaker***. <https://isea2022.isea-international.org/event/canodrom-panels/>.
- Round Table1 and 2: “*Participación Ciudadana, Ética y Género*” and “*Carreras en Salud Digital y Data Science*” - **Barcelona Biomedicine Women in Data Science (WiDS)** (September 2022) by *María José Rementeria and Atia Cortés as **invited speaker***. <https://sites.google.com/isglobal.org/wids-congress-2022/>.

- UK Conference of Bioinformatics and Computational Biology (UK-CBCB) – **Earlham Institute** (September 2022) “*The Bioinfo4Women programme: promoting gender equity and diversity for science at the BSC*” by Alba Jené as **invited speaker**. <https://www.earlham.ac.uk/uk-cbcb-2022#programme>.
- El-lipse Round table on *Racial and Gender biases in Technology and Medicine* – **PRBB** (November 2022) by Davide Cirillo and Nataly Buslón as **invited speaker** <https://ellipse.prbb.org/round-table-on-racial-and-gender-biases-in-technology-and-medicine/>.
- Master Class of 4th year of Engineering and Information and Communication Technologies – **Universitat Pompeu Fabra** (November 2022). “Addressing sex bias in large-scale human data repositories worldwide” by Davide Cirillo as **invited speaker**.

Objective 4. Start local or regional B4W nodes.

B4W approached senior researchers who were a part of the B4W-fellows programme about starting their own local or regional nodes. The recommendation is to begin by setting up seminars and other small initiatives that enhance and promote women's scientific careers following the steps of the B4W. This goal has not been achieved so far.

To connect the nodes and form an active network, B4W will actively participate in organised seminars and activities.

Objective 5.- Include in the B4W programme female researchers with the possibility of being nominated for the International Society for Computational Biology (ISCB) awards.

There were no candidates proposed for the ISCB awards due to a lack of time to understand the procedure and come up with candidates. However, it is worth highlighting other awards and recognitions received by women researchers in the Life Science Department in 2022:

- Atia Cortés designated member of the Spanish National Ethics Committee.
- Eva Alloza, designated ELIXIR Training Platform co-lead.
- Marta Melé awarded with “Knowledge of Talent” award.
- Marta Villegas awarded the ARCHILETRAS award (for the initiative taken in cities for linguistics) <https://www.archiletras.com/actualidad/el-rey-recibe-a-los-galardonados-con-los-premios-archiletras/>.

- Marina Marcet-Houben, listed in the top-5000 cited Spanish women scientists ranking by CSIC <https://www.webometrics.info/en/investigadoras>

- Winona Oliveros awarded the best talk award at the X Genomics and Bioinformatics symposium JBG2022 (SCB_iec). <https://sway.office.com/3C9Nvjhi9Zj9EPyL>.
- Raquel Garcia. Poster award in Genome Informatics 2022.
- Valentina Olmo. Poster award in 9th Advanced Lecture Course on Human Fungal Pathogens (FEBS2022) https://fems-microbiology.org/about_fems/network-and-activities/awards/poster-oral-presentation-prizes/fems-yeast-research-poster-prize-valentina-del-olmo-toledo/.

Additionally, the BSC presented the B4W programme to the EU Award for Gender Equality Champions (https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/prizes/eu-award-gender-equality-champions_en). The outcome is still pending as of January 2023.

Mentoring and Training Objectives

Objective 1.- Launch B4W pilot mentoring programme

To provide young researchers with role models and help them progress their scientific careers to assume positions of responsibility, B4W launched a pilot mentoring programme in June 2022 addressed at PhD students in the Life Science department, and to which two external junior postdoctoral researchers were also invited. The pilot Programme connects BSC mentees with prestigious international scientists as mentors, and it offers professional training to both mentors and mentees to help them organise and carry out mentoring sessions. The costs of the training sessions are covered by the B4W programme.

Nine mentor-mentee pairs have been formed since the mentoring programme's start and have been meeting at least every 6 weeks. The pilot will conclude after one year (May 2023), and its evaluation will serve as the foundation to establish a more ambitious programme addressed at

providing support to senior women postdoctoral researchers who are transitioning to independent positions.

Preliminary feedback on the training received by mentors has been outstanding (see <https://f1000research.com/posters/11-1554> for details), and informal feedback on the follow-up sessions (with a professional coach for mentors, informal discussion with each mentee by B4W organisers) is very positive. The communication flow between mentees and B4W has been excellent and allowed to solve an issue when a mentor-mentee pair had to be re-assigned.

This pilot mentoring programme served as the seed for other future projects:

- A mentoring-based leadership programme for women in middle management in ELIXIR is under development in partnership with ELIXIR-DE and scheduled to launch in June 2023.
- The mentoring Working Group for young researchers of the Women, Science and Innovation Observatory (OMCI) of the Ministry of Science and Innovation has included the mentorship programme as an example of best practice, along with 38 other national and international programmes.

In 2022 there was one training activity organised together with the Women in Bioinformatics and Data Science Latin America (WBDSLAL):

- “Introducción a la Filogenia Viral y análisis de datos con Python” (March 2022). Online hands-on workshop. The course contents included introduction to viral phylogeny and Python, and data analysis with Pandas, including examples with SARS-CoV-2 data. The 3,5-hour workshop was designed for a beginner level and open to Spanish speakers. The pre-registration doubled the 30 trainees capacity of the course. The design and delivery of the course was nicely shared by both organisations, Mónica Cabrera and Victoria Ruiz contributed from B4W as trainers and Eva Alloza took part in the logistics and communication.

Research Line Objectives

Objective 1.- Include the sex and gender perspective in the life science department

The B4W Research Working Group has organized its work into mini-projects that will allow for short execution and rapid publication. Initiatives for existing mini-projects in 2022 are:

- Development of “Sex & Gender Dimension in research projects” Guidelines. A set of guidelines targeting different levels of audiences (master and PhD students, postdocs and PIs, technicians and software/database engineers) is being written up. The materials generated by expert content creators in the context of the EOSC-Life Training project will be used to further enrich the guidelines.

- Assemble a database (papers, datasets, etc.) with scientific evidence regarding the topics: Sex & Gender bias in health and AI. In collaboration with the BSC Project Management Office (PMO), specifically the documentalist Katia Pistrin, B4W is creating a software to mine bibliographic resources, namely Google Scholar, by querying specific keywords. The tool will be used to access and share high-quality literature focusing on specific topic of interest, such as sex differences in health and disease, as well as to assess the level of sex and gender bias in the algorithm for content ranking that is used by Google Scholar.
- Miscarriage and Depression in Twitter (collaboration with Women's Brain Project, WBP and Universitat Oberta de Catalunya, UOC). An analysis of depression in Twitter messages about pregnancy loss was conceived by Davide Cirillo and collaborators in the context of a hackathon organized by the WBP in 2021. The project was carried out in the form of a thesis for the Master's degree in Data Science of Universitat Oberta Catalunya (UOC), co-supervised by Davide Cirillo, and further expanded and refined by the Social Links Analytics Unit and B4W in 2022.
- Participation at the ELIXIR Biohackathon Europe 2022. In November, B4W participated in the Biohackathon organized by ELIXIR with a competitively selected project. The project aimed at analysing the scientific literature to uncover sex imbalance in the published research. The project leveraged the EuroPMC repository to access and mine the context of free-text articles published there.

03 OTHER ACHIEVEMENTS

In addition to the activities aimed at achieving the annual objectives, the B4W programme has carried out the following activities during 2022:

[Gender section of the Severo Ochoa institutional BSC project](#)

B4W through María José Rementería developed the gender part of the Severo Ochoa (SO) proposal presented by the BSC. The SO proposal was granted at the end of 2022. It includes the development of initiatives aimed at attracting and retaining female talent in the BSC, the management of cultural change within the institution toward a more intersectional and inclusive culture, and the expansion of the line of research on women's health and emerging technologies (AI).

[Second BSC Gender Equality Plan \(GEP\)](#)

The B4W has actively participated in the elaboration of the second Gender Equity Plan at the BSC. The GEP plan deployed several actions as the working from home policy and other personnel and work life balance measures, online international recruitment, outreach activities fostering the scientific female figure, improvement of the protocol of action in case of discrimination, mobbing, and sexual harassment in BSC, amongst others.

[Observatorio Mujeres, Ciencia e Innovación \(OMCI\) Working Group](#)

B4W actively participates in the “Observatorio Mujeres, Ciencia e Innovación (OMCI)” working group “Elaboración de una guía con recomendaciones prácticas para la integración de la dimensión de género en los proyectos de I+D+i” at the Ministry of Science and Innovation through María José Rementería. Additionally, it provides feedback on the successful practices, knowledge, and outcomes achieved in the pilot mentoring programme.

[Integration of the sex and gender dimension in life sciences research \(Funded by EOSC-Life\)](#)

A project proposal was successfully prepared and funded in late 2022 under the EOSC-Life training programme. This project will develop the contents to train future researchers how to introduce a sex and gender dimension into life science research projects. The materials created will be used to deliver a hybrid course aimed at future trainers as example and deposited in public repositories to make them available free of cost to the scientific community.

The proposed training will provide methodological tools and specific case studies, showcasing projects funded under Horizon 2020 and illustrating a successful sex and gender integration into key Research and Innovation areas. The timeline to run the project is January-June 2023.

B4W Research Seminars series

- **Rachel Lowe**, London School of Hygiene & Tropical Medicine. “*Strengthening global health resilience to climate change*” invited speaker (20 January 2022). <https://youtu.be/cskLHA35h1w>.
- **Shilpa Garg**, University of Copenhagen. “*Advanced computational approaches for understanding allele-specific biology of complex diseases*” invited speaker (17 February 2022). <https://youtu.be/X9Topdlyk3s>.
- **Silvia Osuna**, ICREA at University of Girona. “*The challenge of rationally predicting distal activity-enhancing mutations in computational enzyme design*” invited speaker (23 June 2022). <https://youtu.be/Zq4Wb04YaOU>.
- **Noelia Ferruz**, University of Girona. “*Towards controlled protein design with deep unsupervised models*” invited speaker (4 July 2022). <https://youtu.be/hWWbKda97H8>.
- **Carole Goble**, University of Manchester. “*Love, Money, Fame, Nudge: Enabling Data-intensive BioScience through Digital Infrastructure Nudging.*” invited speaker (21 July 2022).

- **Tandy Warnow**, University of Illinois. “*New Approaches for Phylogenetic Species Tree Estimation*” invited speaker (22 September 2022). <https://youtu.be/mvn67X315kk>.
- **Eva Novoa**, CRG - Novoa Lab. “*Decoding the epitranscriptome at single molecule resolution*” invited speaker (15 December 2022). <https://youtu.be/PynbOB-tzQM>.

B4W Fellows Programme

Since 2018, B4W has been developing the "B4W Fellows" program to support young researchers in starting their independent research group.

Negotiations with Human Resources were held in September to legally formalise the program due to the new Spanish regulations and laws and to incorporate and finance through the Severo Ochoa Project.

04 PEER- REVIEWED PUBLICATIONS

- **Sex and Gender Bias in Technology and Artificial Intelligence (Book).** A systematic revision on the details of the integration of sex and gender as critical factors in innovative technologies for biomedicine and healthcare application. It aims to provide a critical understanding of the fundamental issues regarding the relationships between sex and gender, health and technology and the biases that appear in AI. <https://www.elsevier.com/books/sex-and-gender-bias-in-technology-and-artificial-intelligence/cirillo/978-0-12-821392-6>
- **Raising Awareness of Sex and Gender in Artificial intelligence and Health (Article publication in process).** The Bioinfo4women (B4W) program of the Barcelona Supercomputing Center promotes the participation of women scientists by improving their visibility, fosters international collaborations and advances research on sex and gender bias in AI and health. In this article, we discuss methodology and results of a series of conferences, organized by B4W and La Caixa Foundation from March to June 2021 in Barcelona, Spain. Based on this awareness-raising action, we distilled key recommendations to facilitate the inclusion of sex and gender perspective into public policies, educational programs, industry, and biomedical research, among other sectors, and help overcome sex and gender biases in AI and health.
- **Addressing sex bias in biological databases worldwide, Biohackathon 2021 (Manuscript in BioHackrXiv (<https://biohackrxiv.org/n9dkg>), peer-review expected by 2023).** This paper focuses on the relevance of variables such as sex, age, or race for tailored treatments for precision medicine and the use of said variables on clinical studies and sample records. When these fields are not specified, it can result in biased predictions as they will not be considered in the training of the AI algorithm. In this work we quantified biases in sex classification over time in human data from studies deposited in EGA and the database of Genotypes and Phenotypes (dbGaP), which represents the EGA's equivalent in the USA. The main result is that the EGA policy is effective to fight sex classification biases because there are significantly less samples classified as unknown after 2018 in this repository than in dbGaP. Additionally, we qualitatively assessed public opinion on this issue.
- **Biohackathon 2022 (Article in progress).** Continuing the work from the *Biohackathon 2021* We developed a pipeline to obtain the entire available repository from EuroPMC and assessed the partition of sex within two databases, EGA and dbGaP. In this paper, we concentrate on the scientific literature to uncover sex imbalance in the published research annotated the relevant information regarding mentions of sex collected in a dataset. From that annotated dataset we train a model to automatically extract the number of female and/or male present in the articles/research. That data extraction allows us to describe the current state of the articles published on EuropePMC.